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AMP-SCZ PoP Team E Cognition SOP

Version 1.1

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ProCAN

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VERSION HISTORY

Version	Date	Summary of Changes
1.0	2025 Aug 15	N/A

A. Cognitive Assessment Batteries

A.1 **The Penn Computerized Neurocognitive Battery (Penn CNB)** includes 8 subtests. Tasks are administered via laptop computer and facilitated by a site study coordinator. Task and order of administration is as follows:

Test Order	Test Acronym	Test Name	Length (mins)
1	SPLLT	Short Penn List Learning Test	3
2	MPRACT	Motor Praxis Test	2
3	SPCPTNL	Short Penn Continuous Performance Test	5
4	ER40	Penn Emotion Recognition Test	3.5
5	SFNB2	Short Fractal N-Back Test	10
6	DIGSYM	Digit-Symbol Test	3
7	SVOLT	Short Visual Object Learning Test	2.5
8	SCTAP	Short Computerized Finger-Tapping Test	3.5
		Total	32.5

A.2 **The Cambridge Neuropsychological Test Automated Battery (CANTAB)** is administered via laptop and facilitated by a site study coordinator. Three subtests from the CANTAB were selected for administration in this project, as follows:

Test Order	Test Acronym	Test Name	Length (mins)
1	SWM	Spatial Working Memory	4
2	RVP	Rapid Visual Information Processing	6
3	LIT	Latent Inhibition	10
		Total	20

A.3 **Administration:** Penn CNB and CANTAB measures are expected to be administered in an in-person single session lasting approximately 55-60 minutes, inclusive of breaks. A break will be offered to all participants within the Penn CNB and between Penn CNB and the CANTAB administration, or as requested by participants at appropriate times (e.g. between subtests).

Both CANTAB and PennCNB assessments will be completed by participants at site, using laptops at the site.

The following are permitted systems and browsers that can be used:

Windows Operating System Version 10, 11

Browser: Chrome, Firefox, Edge

A wired mouse should be connected for the participant to use during the completion of the CANTAB tasks, please do not permit use of a wireless mouse or track pad.

Please ensure you enter **full screen mode** for the completion of assessments. The participant should not exit full screen mode during completion of the assessments, this will prevent the participant from exiting the Connect platform or navigating to other windows.

Note: You will need to create a unique SubjectID to register a session and administer the battery. For practice purposes, the unique SUBJECT ID should be your initials followed by the date in MMDDYYYY format. For example, the test links for the CNB Standardized Assessment session with William S. Stone would have the subject ID of '=WSS08312025' for the assessment date of August 31, 2025.

PennCNB: Launch the Rater application via this link: <https://webcnp.med.upenn.edu> and click “start testing”.

CANTAB: Launch the Rater application via this link: <https://app.cantab.com/rater/>

When testing a **new participant**, select the Test a new Participant button. Existing participants are selected from ‘**Test an existing Participant**’ option:

For each assessment, ensure the correct Visit is displayed at the bottom of the screen. You can manually update the visit by clicking on the visit bar to display all visits and selecting the correct visit to be administered.

B. Training and QC

A “train the trainer” model will be implemented, such that the Team E co-leads (Dr. Bill Stone and Dr. Eve Lewandowski) will train at least one suitably qualified representative at each site in the cognition battery (described in detail below) administration. Prior to test administration, training will cover general rapport, creating favorable test environments to the extent possible, and will discuss how the REDCap forms should be used as a guide and completed.

B.1 Penn Battery (WebCNP) training. Drs. Bill Stone, Eve Lewandowski, and Setari Parsa will train representatives from each site in their respective networks by Zoom. Training times will be established.

Direct training on the PennCNB administration is conducted via links sent directly from Penn to individual raters. Administration accuracy is checked, and certification is determined (pass/fail) and issued through the Penn site. This training involves administration of the full PennCNB curated for this project. Of note, training and certification process for the PennCNB is **not identical to that of ProNET**.

The Penn CNB tests are intended to be administered to participants remotely via the screen-share feature on Zoom. We are requesting that all sites employ this version of a remote protocol to maintain procedural uniformity and continuity. **Thus, while tests may be administered to a**

participant who is on-site, they should be done using two separate computer locations/rooms.

For the Penn CNB, a link will be sent to the participant to access the tests (see the Penn CNB section for further details). Note that email addresses and other PII are not recorded.

All Penn CNB tests are scored automatically.

Only variable values within established ranges of acceptable scores will be accepted. All response times must have non-zero values.

All coding changes will be followed by testing output prior to implementation in the study.

You should also review the Administrator Manual, which is available on the WebCNB website (link below). Use the practice account credentials below (and on the [GitHub wiki](#)) to log in. This should serve as a reference guide even post CNB certification once you have begun assessing for a project.

Username: training

Password:

Administrator Manual: <https://webcnp.med.upenn.edu/manuals.pl?name=manual>

<https://github.com/upenn/cnb-pub/wiki>

After completing the modules 1-4, review the additional ProctTrack training video. Paste the link below on your browser's search bar as is, do not just click on it.

<https://upenn.box.com/s/3iozwhgs0bt0ah5ygb44d3xj6vo244qi>

Then, you are **strongly encouraged** to practice administering the full PennCNB and CANTAB procedures a minimum of 4 times (start to finish) to a practice participant before you record your Standardized Assessment video. Use the practice account to practice and record your video. **The best way to record the video is to use a video conference software (ex: Zoom, Teams, GoTo Meeting, BlueJeans) as your "meeting room". **

The 4 alternate forms of the SPLLT and the other PennCNB tests will be administered through separate links. Please note, you will need to administer **BOTH** batteries (administer the SPLLT battery first, followed by the NOSPLLT battery) to administer the "full CNB assessment". Please refer to the Full Assessment Video in the CNB Training and Certification Platform for procedures.

(The practice account is only for use in practice sessions and should NOT be used to assess participants upon completion of the CNB training process)

B.2 CANTAB training. Drs. Bill Stone, Eve Lewandowski, and Setari Parsa will train representatives from each site by Zoom. Training times will be established, to be run concurrently with the PennCNB trainings.

Direct training on CANTAB administration is conducted via links sent directly from the CANTAB team to individual raters. Administration accuracy will be checked and certification issued

through the CANTAB team. This training involves the administration of the three CANTAB measures included in this project.

Logging into Connect

On being granted access to Connect each user will receive an email from noreply@cantab.com. The email will include a link (“confirm password”) to enable the user to create and confirm a secure password. Click on the link and then enter and confirm your password, and then press submit.

Training is administered via Practice Accounts ONLY. Practice accounts for CANTAB should not be used to assess participants upon completion of the CANTAB training process.

You should also carefully review the CANTAB Administrator Manual available at <https://camcog.sharepoint.com/sites/CPMTeamFiles/>.

C. Quality Assurance

C.1 PennCNB

Automated QC protocols are built into the PennCNB. Additionally, out of range indicators are built into data forms at DPACC to flag out of range values.

Manual QC: After certification, Dr. Parsa will review administration procedures for accuracy with the first study participant seen by each rater, and then periodically afterwards.

Rater comments will be reviewed periodically by Drs. Stone, Lewandowski and Parsa.

C2. CANTAB

Validation rules are programmed within the CANTAB Connect platform to ensure the user is prompted with an alert message for any potential data error at the point of data collection. For example, when a user runs a visit that is duplicate or out of sequence, user is prompted to provide a reason which is recorded as an audit trail at the point of selection of visit. This reason for change is then available along with the relevant query for the site and DM to review, approve, or reject. This query management system within Connect ensures traceability of data changes along with the record of site communication.

The automatic validation rules programmed in Connect platform triggers queries, which are as follows:

1. Duplicate visit
2. Out of sequence visit
3. Duplicate subject

4. Missed visit

There are two types of validation within the Connect platform: Automatic Data Validation and Manual Data Validation.

The automatic validation checks and options for resolution are conducted after each assessment. These checks will result in data queries being generated by the CANTAB Connect system for site personnel with Query Resolver access privilege to propose a resolution to. Once a resolution has been proposed by the user at site, the Cambridge Cognition Data Management team will review the proposed resolution and either accept or reject the resolution. Rejected resolutions will be returned to site for further review and resolution along with a detailed explanation of the reason for rejection. An email will be sent to the query resolver(s) at site to inform them of the number of open queries and ask for updated resolutions to be provided within 5 working days.

If a proposed resolution to a data query has been rejected more than twice, or if a resolution has not been proposed within 5 working days, the Cambridge Cognition Clinical Project Manager or Data Manager may contact the site via email or telephone to provide further information or assistance and seek a timely resolution. If a timely/ clear resolution is still not provided, details of any outstanding queries may be escalated to the CRO, Client and/or Sponsor.

If a consistent pattern or high number of queries becomes evident, Cambridge Cognition Clinical Project Manager or Data Manager will escalate to the CRO, Client and/or Sponsor representative for further training and resolution.

The manual validation checks are conducted by the Cambridge Cognition Data Management or Clinical Project Management teams through review of the data and action as appropriate.

Manual visit query: Within the Connect system the Cambridge Cognition team can raise a manual visit query to propose to move or delete a visit or reinstate a deleted visit. Manual queries may be raised to correct discrepancies in the data identified through data reconciliation activities, or when the Client, Sponsor, CRO or site report an issue via email or phone/helpdesk support. The manual query will contain details of where the information regarding the data discrepancy was received from (e.g. Client/Sponsor/CRO/Site/reconciliation). These manual queries will be reviewed by site personnel who can accept or reject the proposal. Rejected proposals will be returned to Cambridge Cognition for further clarification.

Where queries are raised in error, or have already been resolved through a separate query, the query may be closed internally by two independent Cambridge Cognition team members.

Should a consistent pattern or high number of queries become evident, Cambridge Cognition Clinical Project Manager or Data Manager will escalate to the CRO, Client and/or Sponsor for further training and resolution.

Helpful advice from the CNB Team:

Cognitive Assessment Order of Procedures

1. Welcome participant and introduce the PennCNB and CANTAB
2. Confirm cell phones are off
3. Administer all tasks in the Penn CNB battery followed by CANTAB tasks, making sure to update PennCNB ProctTrack as the battery progresses
4. Make sure to offer the break point at the halfway mark!
5. When Cognitive assessment is completed, thank the participant for their efforts!
6. When you have a moment without the participant present, enter any remaining notes into the virtual platform ([ProctTrack](#)).

PennCNB Mock Data Upload:

1. Go to <https://webcnp.med.upenn.edu> and click “start testing”.
 2. Log in with the practice account information.
 3. For the SPLLT:
 - a. Select the SPLLT-A battery from the dropdown.
 - b. Select the PRACTICE site.
 - c. Enter one of your site’s test IDs.
 4. Practice with a colleague/ friend or you can run through this on your own to enter answers.
 5. After the SPLLT, repeat steps 3 & 4 but select the ProNET_NOSPLLT battery.
 6. Once completed, please submit a run sheet (labeled “Penn CNB”) in REDCap using the corresponding test ID.
- a. *Site:* Each site has its own unique site ID, which will appear in the dropdown. Once you are certified, your personal administrator account will be already loaded with the correct site ID you will need access to.
- b. *Subject:* Enter the subject’s AMPSCZ ID which is the usual 2 letters then 5 numbers (e.g., XX12345).
- c. *Visit:* After the visit, go to [Edit Sessions page](#)¹ and complete the visit ID field with 1, 2, 3, or 4 according to this chart below:
- i. Screening = 1
 - ii. Baseline = 2
 - iii. Day 29 = 3
 - iv. Day 56 **or** Early Termination = 4

After Certification:

Email the PennCNB and CANTAB to obtain your personal administrator account and access to the test platform (CANTAB). In your email, include your full name and site. Your personal account will have access to all 6 relevant batteries.

Visit #	Battery 1	Battery 2
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¹ Full instructions on Editing Sessions can be found in the administrator manual, section Assessment Procedures.

1	SPLLT-A	NOSPLLT
2	SPLLT-B	NOSPLLT_b
3	SPLLT-C	NOSPLLT
4	SPLLT-D	NOSPLLT_b

For any direct queries about the PennCNB please contact:

Setari Parsa (sparsa@bidmc.harvard.edu)

For any direct queries about the CANTAB please contact:

Julie-Ann Marshall (julie-ann.marshall@camcog.com)

Administration Schedule

Day	Screening			Day 1				Day 29		Day 56		Early Withdrawal
NEUROCOGNITION (assess first)												
PennCNB	X											
Short Penn List Learning Test (SPLLT)	X ^a			X ^b				X ^c		X ^d		X ^d
Motor Praxis Test (MPRACT)	X			X				X		X		X
Short Penn Continuous Performance Test (SPCPTNL)	X			X				X		X		X
Penn Emotion Recognition Test (ER40)	X			X				X		X		X
Break Point												
Short Fractal N-Back Test (SFNB2)	X			X				X		X		X
Digit Symbol Test (DIGSYM)	X			X				X		X		X
Short Visual Object Learning Test (SVOLT)	X ^a			X ^b				X ^a		X ^b		X ^b
Short Computerized Finger Tapping Test (SCTAP)	X			X				X		X		X
CANTAB SWM	X			X				X		X		X
CANTAB RVP	X			X				X		X		X
CANTAB LIT				X								

X^a – alternate test version 'a'; X^b – alternate test version 'b'; X^c - alternate test version 'c'; X^d - alternate test version 'd'; X – no alternate versions of test